

GlaS - - Fuels

Single-Atom Photocatalysts Enhanced by a Self-Powered Photonic Glass Reactor to Produce Advanced Biofuels

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5 Partners | 4 Countries | 2.99M Total Budget | 42 Months

Technology

Incorporation of functional thermoelectric composite polymers and highly luminescent perovskite films in the photonic glass reactor

Use of femtosecond (fs) laser-processing to enhance the optical and emission properties of the photonic glass reactor

Engineering of single-atom catalysts with photo-triggered functions for 2G biofuels